

1 A neuronal pentraxin receptor, NPTXR2, is among the molecules whose expression was most significantly
2 activated during resistance to chemotherapy and present at highest quantities in the TNBC cell.

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10 Citations

11 1. Zhou, J., Wade, S.D., Graykowski, D., Xiao, M.F., Zhao, B., Giannini, L.A., Hanson, J.E., van
12 Swieten, J.C., Sheng, M., Worley, P.F. and Dejanovic, B., 2022. Neuronal pentraxin Nptx2 regulates
13 complement activity in the brain. bioRxiv, pp.2022-09.